

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL TRAINING AND THE RESULTING PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION THAT AFFECTS THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL THINKING

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ABSTRACT

The given article reveals the importance of the teacher's professional development in the implementation of the pedagogical and psychological features of the teacher's professional training and development today, as well as the extremely important role of professional thinking in the teacher's communication. In addition, the research highlights the importance of developing students' professional thinking through pedagogical communication, as well as the extremely important role of professional thinking in patient-physician communication, particularly, among students of higher educational medical institutions.

Introduction

The actuality of the given research lies in the growing need for highly qualified specialists and, in connection with this, in the need to study the characteristics of the psychological readiness of students - future teachers - for professional activities at the final stage of education at the university. Today there is an acute problem of professional competition in the labor market. In the context of rapidly changing social, economic and political challenges, the professional competencies of future specialists are of key importance. The professional activity of specialists is becoming more and more complex, and new requirements for employees are increasing every day. Therefore, fundamentally new requirements are also imposed on the activities of higher educational institutions.

As the president of our republic Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted, "Undoubtedly, confidence in our own strength and capabilities unites us on the noble goal of creating the foundations of the Third Renaissance, making us stronger and stronger. These aspirations are turning into great practical works, and the great people's movement is expanding more and more. It is a great happiness, a great honor to be in such a powerful line"[1] Accordingly, in this process, a teacher-educator can be kind and generous to students from a human point of view, and can teach them based on the students of the time, only if they have high spirituality, morals, manners, and moral culture. For this, first

of all, he should be intellectual - intelligent, generous, determined, willing, open-minded, demanding, kind and benevolent towards himself and students, and able to approach his personality from a critical point of view. is required. While participating in the process of raising a mature generation, the future teacher should not only be an example to others with his spiritual and moral culture, but at the same time, he should be able to demonstrate his skills based on his professional thinking, and train qualified personnel as mature pedagogues. it is necessary to make a proper contribution to the work of preparation.

In our republic, a number of scientific researches have been carried out in various periods regarding the specific ethnopsychological qualities, characteristics, abilities, working methods, ways to achieve mastery, and interpersonal communication norms of the teaching profession.

Communication is a process of interaction between communication subjects, during this interaction information is exchanged, relations are established and developed. Collaborative activities are organized and implemented through communication. At the same time, during the activity, new relations and connections are formed between people. So, communication and activity are closely related.

It should be mentioned that the realization of the educational potential of communication is largely determined by the personal qualities of the teacher. A properly chosen method of pedagogical communication, consistent with the unique individuality of the pedagogue, helps to solve the following set of tasks:

1. Firstly, pedagogical influence becomes the same thing as the personality of the pedagogue, the process of communicating with the audience becomes simpler, it becomes pleasant and organic for the pedagogue;
2. Secondly, the process of establishing mutual relations with students becomes much easier;
3. Thirdly, the effectiveness of all the most important tasks of pedagogical communication increases, at the same time, all this happens on the positive basis of emotional calmness of the pedagogue at all stages of communication.

The aim of the given scientific article is to identify and systematize the fundamental pedagogical and psychological characteristics of the training of qualified teachers, as well as the analysis of pedagogical communication in the educational process between the teacher and students in order to improve their professional thinking.

Materials And Methods

The methodology of forming an individual style of communication in students includes the following stages:

1. Studying the real personal characteristics of the individual style of student communication and students' understanding of them. It is carried out on the basis of independent analysis of students, comprehensive descriptions of each other, observations of teachers. For this purpose, students asked "How am I in communication with other people?" they write essays on the topic, prepare descriptions for each other with a similar content, etc.
2. Actions to identify shortcomings in personal communication and eliminate them: overcoming shyness, embarrassment, negative situations in the communication style.
3. Tasks on developing an emotionally comfortable style of communication for a teacher and their comparison with self-observation data.

4. Work in the field of mastering the components of pedagogical communication based on one's own individual style of communication (in special training).
5. In accordance with one's own style of communication, work on learning the whole phenomenon of pedagogical communication and clarifying the style of communication (in special trainings).
6. Communicating with students based on an individual style of real pedagogical activity, strengthening this style (during pedagogical practice and internship).

It is necessary for teachers who are just starting to work in medical colleges to regularly work on the formation of individual communication style.

Professional skills, high pedagogical thinking, a conscious, creative approach to the educational process, the ability to effectively apply methodical knowledge, which is to constantly improve pedagogical knowledge, to be aware of news, to use advanced technologies. is composed based on mastery. Future teachers, as well as young teachers, are provided with professional skills by following a number of conditions for professional self-improvement. They consist of studying the activities of experienced teachers is organized without leaving the educational institution and is considered effective from the time and economic point of view; Studying the activities of experienced teachers is carried out on the basis of observation and analysis of the training organized by them, it is appropriate to draw a conclusion based on the generalization of the impressions received in this regard.

Consequently, a person who does not understand the essence of the pedagogical process and does not have deep respect for the student will not have an opinion that ensures the effectiveness of education and human maturity. The basis of the pedagogical culture of the future teacher is the ability to understand the student, to have a humane attitude towards him, to correctly assess the situation, to eliminate potential conflicts in time, the rightness of pedagogical activity, the development of society and the belief that the noble ideas instilled in the minds of students in the pedagogical process are a powerful factor and tool in ensuring the existence of life.

Results And Discussion

In the implementation of pedagogical and psychological features of teacher's professional training and development, the stages of teacher's professional development are divided into 4 main stages, as mentioned in the table above, and each stage is formed based on its own content and criteria.

Concerning the results of the considered study, Gonobolin, in his pamphlet named "The Story of a Teacher", thinks on behalf of the teacher Vera Aleksandrovna Raush, and describes a skilled teacher as follows: "I think that in order to become a good teacher, first of all, you need to live a real life, to strive for a full-blooded life directed to a certain goal. It is necessary to study nature and observe its laws, read books, listen to music, go to theaters, go on trips, etc. In order to share it with others, a pedagogue needs to absorb a lot of things in his heart. That's why I constantly turn to books, learn from nature, read constantly, read diligently" [2].

Therefore, in order to become a skilled master of his profession, a teacher will achieve his goal only when he works on himself regularly, enjoys nature, art, life, science, develops and becomes perfect. Master of human psychology F.N. As Gonobolin noted, the teacher gives all his strength, will, knowledge, all the good things he has to his students and the people. However, if he does not give everything he has today, tomorrow, tomorrow, and replenishes

his knowledge, strength, energy again and again, then he will have nothing left. On the one hand, the teacher should give his best, and on the other hand, like a cloud, he should get used to receiving good things from life, science, and work in cooperation with the most advanced people of the nation. In that case, no matter how much he gives to his students, if he can learn the best qualities from the people, life, and science, then he will always have more and more such nourishing juices for his students. will be available [3].

Based on the above, the following can be pointed out as the main directions of educating an independent thinker, a creative person with a professional mindset in the educational process today:

- "industrialization of education", i.e. strengthening the intellectual activity of modern society based on computerization and technology;
- transition from informational forms of education, which prevailed until now, to active teaching methods and forms. This direction consists of the transition from the "school of memory" to the "school of understanding" and "school of thought";
- transition from strictly defined control methods to developing, activating, improving methods and game methods in the organization and management of the educational process. This creates an opportunity to support and develop the organizational-creative, independent activity of learners;
- organizing activities of mutual cooperation between the learner and the pedagogue, that is, ensuring the participation of learners as a joint team activity. In this case, the main emphasis is transferred from the teacher's knowledge-giving activity to the student's learning activity. From our observation of the educational processes aimed at the formation of independent thinking and creativity among students of the Bukhara State Medical Institute, it is known that there are many and various ways of realizing an independent thinking, creative person in the process of education.

We can list the following as the main ones:

- in each lesson, students should not repeat the knowledge that the teacher gave them based on the requirements of the textbook, but should ensure the formation of new knowledge with his guidance. This leads to the formation of the practical skill of seeking knowledge in the learner with the help of thinking;
- in the lesson, the student should not be a passive listener, but a seeker, comparer, discoverer. Therefore, every word, opinion, judgment, and statement that comes out of a student's mouth must be his own. Of course, this thought born in a student may not be a universal discovery or a solution to a complicated problem, nor a simple repetition of information given by a teacher (textbook). This method of education serves to educate the student's independence, responsibility, self-awareness, creativity, and creative spirit. As a result, the communication between the teacher and the students in the course of the lesson can take the form of lively verbal communication and debate in many cases;
- the guide to research and thinking given by the teacher to the learner should be such that the product of research and creativity of the students in the group is not exactly the same - it is essentially in the same direction, but different in form It is necessary. Only then, each learner will have the opportunity to express himself as brightly as possible, and the spirit of competition will lead them in every training;
- in the course of the lesson (doing homework and analyzing it in the classroom, in the

auditorium), the student searches, thinks, finds something, comes to a conclusion and judgment based on the teacher's instructions, and seeks to justify, prove, and defend his opinion. is necessary.

In addition, the organization of the training and the educational material should open a wide path for this, should be suitable for the young psychology and mental-physiological potential of the learner. At this point, it should be noted that today many textbooks and training manuals are being prepared with content aimed at students' independent thinking and nurturing their creativity. In particular, educational programs and textbooks on subjects created in accordance with State educational standards in general education, secondary special education, vocational education and higher education system "About Education" is being prepared based on the criteria and scientific principles defined in the new version of the law.

Undoubtedly, they consist of materials within the scope of things and events connected with the student's lifestyle and daily life, and are designed for the level of psychological development of learners at each age level.

The step-by-step sequence in the delivery of new content textbooks and assignments, the ways in which the practice of developing the student's mental activity in the process of learning each topic becomes more complicated from topic to topic, from class to class, from stage to stage, and from active observation of the learning process to practical ones. The process of ending with application is also fully compatible with the conscious verbal cognitive psychodidactic framework.

Aspects of pedagogical communication play an important role in the organization of the educational process, they are related to the direct interaction of the pedagogue and students. Here are some steps:

1. The first stage is the educator's awareness of the situation of the educational process, this process requires the pedagogue to restore the previous features of communication with the group in his memory, to record the situation of communication, to quickly compare it with the previous situation of the interaction, with the previously planned example of this action, involves clarifying the communication style. It should be noted that this stage passes very quickly, and at the same stage, the necessary words, tone, behavior should appear.

2. Second stage: For the effective process of pedagogical communication, it is not enough to know its conditions. The beginning of interaction with students is related to solving another important task of exchange of ideas and attracting the attention of the object of communication. What should be understood by attracting the attention of the object of communication, that is, the student? The meaning of this is to draw the attention of students, which is necessary for conducting the lesson, to take the social-psychological basis for the future interaction, the planned methods of education, organizational forms. Often, young pedagogues think that students should always pay attention to the teacher and do not solve these important tasks of mutual exchange of ideas with a steady step.

The indicated stages of direct communication are relatively independent of pedagogical influence, they are repeated from time to time in each form, they should be taken into account when organizing the educational process.

In connection with the importance of communication in the organization of educational influence, special demands are placed on the culture of pedagogical communication, the

educator's cordiality, cordiality is manifested in it as professional thinking. An educator should be able to communicate with people in the process of team, group and individual work, organize it with students with a specific goal in mind, and be able to manage them. The following criteria of professional pedagogic harmony, which a young teacher follows, can be singled out: the presence of a stable need for regular communication with students in various fields, the manifestation of emotional calmness at all stages of communication, qualities related to mutual exchange of ideas, availability of skills and qualifications.

Here are given some necessary professional characteristics of a teacher for communication:

- Pedagogical delicacy;
- pedagogical empathy;
- accessibility to communication;
- kindness to people, benevolence, encouraging positive communication;
- understanding people's mental state and experiences;
- the ability of pedagogical improvisation;
- Demonstrate verbal and non-verbal skills;
- Operative thinking (G. Kurbanova);
- Creative thinking.

Future teachers of medical institutions should be sharply distinguished by the following characteristics, and these characteristics determine the main criteria of their professional thinking:

- views of a high spiritual level that correspond to the requirements and needs of our independent republic, strong and stable faith, loyalty to the ideals of our great country, the national idea and ideology of independence, the formation of feelings of patriotism, self-sacrifice, perfectly reflecting the sense of community, social - being a politically active person;
- the presence of students, even for all members of our society, the ability, skills and learning to understand their needs, interests, motivations and behaviors;
- pedagogical observation, i.e., perceptive (sensitivity to perception) ability in relation to social events, situations, nature and realities, existence, interpersonal, inter-group, international relations;
- the ability to rationally understand the characteristics of people's actions and relationships in one or another aspect of life and activity, to direct them to identification and reflection;
- the ability to effectively aim, set goals, plan, direct control, manage and express oneself in emergency situations, changing conditions;
- mastery of organization and management skills in pedagogical activities, temporary group relations in the public system, public actions;
- the breadth of the scope of general interest, the variety of interests related to knowledge, the ability to conduct scientific research, the achievement of certain potential, skill levels;
- being armed with communication etiquette, speech culture, logically concise, strong meaning, effective transmission of ideas, ability to influence;

In my opinion, it is a professional necessity for a modern teacher to be able to convey correct, effective information during communication and to be able to convince the interlocutor.

Conclusion

Summing up, I can recommend the following program for mutual exchange of ideas in the process of formation of professional thinking:

1. Self-awareness from a professional point of view (identification of one's own qualities, positive and weak points for mutual exchange of ideas in communication) and the program of self-education through mutual exchange of ideas on this basis development. In this place, it is appropriate to evaluate one's personality in the following directions, to analyze the experience, with students, to analyze the experience of sensations obtained in communication with people, to analyze the current level of previous communication in communication with people, communication to analyze one's own ideal perceptions about, to analyze perceptions of how others (students, teachers) evaluate your communication capabilities.
2. Working on the basis of specialized exercises to develop the main features of self-confidence.
3. Carrying out various public works with students and people, in which the experience of exchanging ideas (lectures, conversations) is created.
4. To create a system of situations that form the experience of overcoming negative moods in communication and develop cordiality.

Working on the basis of this proposed system accelerates the formation of empathy, which is a personal quality of a pedagogue.

Professional thinking, in turn, based on the culture of communication, expresses the worldview of the future teacher, his desire for maturity through his love for his profession, his sense of existence, his sense of necessity for the interests and development of the Motherland, society.

Speaking of pedagogical and psychological characteristics of teacher's professional training I can state undoubtedly, the consistent application of such an educational method in practice, gaining experience in this direction requires correction, addition and clarification. For this, we can list the following as the tasks facing the continuous education system first of all:

- one of our most important tasks should be to popularize the method of verbal cognitive education (a new pedagogical technology of education today) among teachers. Because teachers cannot learn to use modern pedagogical technologies and practical use of visual and technological tools to apply this method, they will not be able to achieve effective results in this field;
- in order to increase the effectiveness of training with textbooks and educational methods, students must be provided with additional sources of information. it consists of information obtained from educational subjects and inquiries from the surrounding people. This is definitely not enough. That is why teachers are provided with an encyclopedic reference, various types of information (explanatory information, situational issues, illustrative materials, etc.) must be taken.

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